

Remodelling Historic Maps - Handling Multi-Categorisation on Thematic Maps

Anastasia Bauch^{*1}

¹Centre for Heritage Conservation Studies and Technologies (KDWT), Otto-Friedrich University of Bamberg, Germany

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Summary

Historic maps of bomb damage from the Second World War offer a rich and under-researched source of information for understanding the post-war destiny of many cities. However, to realise the full potential of these maps it is necessary to digitise them within a GIS environment. In this poster we demonstrate that digitising and comparing historic maps at different levels of detail introduces a number of challenges. Three approaches to tackle these inconsistencies are discussed here with the view of supporting spatial humanities research with these rich sources of information.

KEYWORDS: historic maps, geo-databases, modelling cities, Second World War

1. Context

The UrbanMetaMapping (UMM) project has been concerned with the digitisation of historic analogue maps depicting urban bomb damage during the Second World War (<https://urbanmetamapping.uni-bamberg.de/en>), amongst other objectives. A digitised dataset of maps of the inner city of Nuremberg, Germany during WWII was produced and published open access (Stein et al., 2025). The digitisation was desirable as the original maps contain very detailed information that is hard to analyse manually and visually, especially when comparing multiple large format maps (Ludwig & Alvanides, 2023). In addition, working with scanned and digitised versions preserves the original maps as the materials they are printed on deteriorate over time with extensive use. In the case of Nuremberg, multiple maps of bomb damage were produced during and after the war (Enss & Knauer, 2023) alongside maps depicting additional layers of information (e.g. heritage buildings). To facilitate the study and further analysis of multiple layers of information the UMM project digitised a series of historic maps drawn on the same cadastral basemap. This poster illustrates one of the challenges of converting data from analogue to digital form, as well as different approaches to resolving it.

2. Towards a detailed city model

Based on the cadastral basemap we identified building footprints as the smallest geometric unit for the geo-features. Thematic data from various maps based on the same cadastral basemap was then added to the geo-features as attributes. The seven thematic maps were: The Monument Value Level Map (StadtAN_A4_X_210, estimated date between 1942 and 1945), three consecutive air raid damage maps (StadtAN_A4_X_207-209, dated from January - March of 1945), a map about rubble clearance status

* anastasia.bauch@uni-bamberg.de

† klaus.stein@uni-bamberg.de

‡ carmen.enss@uni-bamberg.de

§ serafeim.alvanides@uni-bamberg.de

(StadtAN_C29_1394_2, no date), the Verified Map of Total Damage (StadtAN_A4_VII_2469, December 1945) and a map about the rebuilding progress (StadtAN_A4_X_265, 1952).** The aim was to compare the data for all geo-features over several maps, producing statistical information towards answering questions such as: “Were historic buildings prioritised in the rebuilding process?” “How did the war damage categories change over the years?” “Are there any consistencies in maps with the same categorisation scheme?” “Were badly damaged buildings more likely to be completely torn down to make space for new city planning?” As a result, we were also able to perform spatial queries, for example to assess if proximity to special buildings or squares made a difference in how damage was mapped or indeed inflicted.

The thematic maps, however, deviated from the basic geometric unit (individual building footprint) e.g. by colouring half a building as destroyed and the other half as slightly damaged, thus breaking the one-to-one mapping of damage level to geo-feature. This meant that we had to decide how to handle these edge cases, since ignoring them would have introduced bias into our data, resulting in loss of detail, either by only one of the categories being introduced into the digital representation or even none of them. We therefore explored three alternative approaches.

2.1 Splitting features

Figure 1 Splitting the base geometries for a source accurate area model of the categorisations.

Splitting the features (polygons) according to the mapped categorisations adds a higher level of detail to the geometry as illustrated in **Figure 1**. This would go hand in hand with the introduction of a geometry hierarchy, where the split geometries from the original building footprint would form together

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that geometry at a higher level of the hierarchy. This approach introduces more complexity to the QGIS project, where the dataset is either represented by more than one layer or by overlapping geometries of the same layer. Because of the emphasis on accurately representing the geometry shown in the source maps, this approach seems valuable when the area of interest is a categorisation. The additional effort of splitting and managing the polygon geometries, especially since the sub-polygons of one building footprint may be different for all the source maps, does not seem feasible for questions that focus on the quantity of buildings that have been at least partially categorised as destroyed, historically valuable, etc.

2.2 Adding attributes

Figure 2 Flagging all features with multi-categorisations.

The introduction of an additional attribute (QGIS field) to mark objects with multiple categorisations for each map, as shown in **Figure 2**, can already help with the reading of the data. A user can then conclude that out of X buildings categorised as heavily damaged, Y buildings have at least one additional categorisation. In the digitisation process this has the advantage of introducing a simple Boolean flag into the QGIS attribute form, that can be checked if necessary. However, this means that users will have to consider the additional attribute in their queries, again increasing the complexity of the model and requiring closer reading of the data to decide whether the additional categorisations carry weight for the particular scientific question. The problem can also be addressed by introducing additional value attributes instead of a simple Boolean flag. This approach would then scale the problem of added complexity by having an open number of additional attributes to query (some buildings have more than 2 categories and so on).

2.1 Multiple categories

Figure 3 Referencing a categorisation table to model multiple categorisations.

To overcome the problem of adding attributes as needed, which makes it difficult to adapt queries to newly added data, we attempted to map multiple categories to a single attribute using value relations, as shown in **Figure 3**. This involves switching from a single category attribute for each map to a multiple category attribute using the QGIS “value relations” widget in the layer attribute form (see: https://docs.qgis.org/3.40/en/docs/user_manual/working_with_vector/joins_relations.html). In the GeoPackage layer we did this using string and JSON attributes containing value relations pointing to a separate value table. For the person digitising the map, this would mean little additional effort, as they would be presented with an attribute form where they would simply check the existing categorisations. QGIS then treats each combination of values as a separate category in the layer styling, as shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 Multi-value attributes as value relations.

However, for classic relational databases, this approach lacks normalisation, and for queries it would be necessary to split the attribute field. In addition, if the value relation is in string format, the data is not properly structured. An alternative for multi-categorisation is provided by the GeoPackage attribute field value option JSON (or the PostgreSQL/PostGIS JSON field), which allows queries on multi-value attributes via extended SQL, as shown in **Figure 5**. The disadvantage of this approach is that the attribute form then becomes a key-value free text format, which makes additions and value management quite tedious compared to maintaining separate value tables.

Figure 5 Querying multi-value attributes.

3. Conclusion

Historic maps of bomb damage from the Second World War offer a rich and under-researched source of information for understanding the postwar destiny of many cities (Elżanowski & Enss, 2022). However, to realise the full potential of these maps in terms of analysing urban morphology and spatial urban history it is necessary to digitise them within a GIS environment for further analysis. We have presented different approaches to reproducing the inconsistent mapping of historical maps in digital geospatial databases. These can be as detailed as the original, but due to the high effort involved, an appropriate level of abstraction from the original source needs to be identified and adapted to the research needs. By presenting three different approaches for representing complex information we encourage spatial humanities projects to critically consider the question of data structures within GIS depending on the research needs of each project.

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References

Elżanowski J, Enss CM (2022). Cartographies of catastrophe: mapping World War II destruction in Germany and Poland. *Urban History*, 49(3):589–611.

Enss CM, Knauer B (2023). *Atlas Kriegsschadenskarten Deutschland: Stadtkartierung und Heritage Making im Wiederaufbau um 1945*. Basel: Birkhäuser Verlag.

Ludwig C, Alvanides S (2023). A Spatio-Temporal Analysis of the Urban Fabric of Nuremberg From the 1940s Onwards Using Historical Maps. *UP*, 8(1). doi:10.17645/up.v8i1.6084.

Stein K, Bauch A, Grallert L, Stauske C, Omonsky L, Enss CM (2025). GIS Dataset Nürnberg War Damage Maps WWII. doi:10.48564/UNIBAFD-HE14F-XH380.

Biographies

Anastasia Bauch studied architecture at the Bauhaus University Weimar and Heritage Science in Bamberg. They are now working on a second Masters in Computing in the Humanities, focusing on the application of geoinformation systems for historical research and communication.

Dr. Klaus Stein is a senior researcher at the Otto-Friedrich-Universität Bamberg. His main research areas are spatial cognition/geo-informatics and social network analysis. He studied Informatics (Computer Science) at the TU München and participated in the interdisciplinary DFG priority program “spatial cognition” for his PhD.

Dr. Carmen M. Enss is a senior researcher and monument conservationist and heads the research network UrbanMetaMapping. She has been conducting research at the the Centre for Heritage Conservation Studies and Technologies (KDWT) at the Otto-Friedrich University Bamberg since 2017.

Dr. Serafeim (Seraphim) Alvanides is a senior researcher for the UMM-Transfer and an urban social geographer with research interests in land use change, urban sprawl, environmental justice and spatial humanities. He has methodological expertise in quantitative methods, urban analytics and geographical information science.